

UNESCO anti-doping programs in Algeria and its contribution to the blockade of the phenomenon

Kesri Nassereddine¹ ; Dahmani Bensadallah²

¹ University of Algiers 3, Institute of Physical Education and Sport, Algeria, ²University of
Amar Thleji (Lagouate), Institute of Physical Education and Sport, Algeria,

¹kesri.nassereddine@univ-alger3.dz .²b.dahmani@lagh-univ.dz .

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Abstract

The study aims to identify the role of UNESCO in the fight against the phenomenon of doping in the sports community through an international fund created by an international convention. Algeria is a member in the convention, we used a descriptive approach on a sample made up of a group within the regions made up of managers, coaches athletes, as it was selectively selected because of those participants in the UNESCO program. Registered n ° 1314 performs in 2015 in three regions. On the other hand, the selection was random via an application (QUIZ. WADA). To collect data, we used an online application to know the level of achievement of participants in the UNESCO program. After collecting the results and processing them statistically, it was concluded that the information obtained is superficial due to the lack of continuous fixation of the information at the level of perception. On this basis, the study recommended that to ensure the achievement of the objectives, it is imperative to set up monitoring cells to continue the consolidation of the principles of the fight against doping and to link them to the morals and ethical conscience of athletes.

Corresponding author:

Kesri Nassereddine

e-mail:

kesri.nassereddine@univ-alger3.dz

I. Introduction

The scientific dictionary defines doping as " the use of illegal drugs, e.g. steroids, in sport" (Heather, Katy and Howard, 2006); competitiveness and the fixation on records in elite sport incite doping. Drug use may help to deliver results as a complement to dedicated training programmes and natural sporting prowess. for an athlete attuned to continual improvement (stronger, higher, faster) performance-enhancing drugs allow for an extension of the physical strength ceiling and greater adaptation (Sale, 1992). Doping seriously threatens the ethics and values upon which sport is based. these principles are embodied in the 1978 International Charter of Physical Education, which was amended in 1991 to refer to the doping problem: no effort must be spared to highlight the harmful effects of doping, which is both injurious to health and contrary to the sporting ethic, or to protect the physical and mental health of athletes, the virtues of fair play and competition, the integrity of the sporting community and the rights of people participating in it at any level whatsoever (UNESCO,1978).

Anti-doping programmes, therefore, seek to preserve the essence of sport characterised by values such as honesty, fairness, respect, courage, commitment and solidarity; the harm caused by the use of performance-enhancing drugs and methods is a compelling rationale for action.

there is incontrovertible scientific evidence about the biomedical side effects of doping on the cardiovascular, musculoskeletal, reproductive, endocrine, immune and respiratory systems. (WADA, 2003).

It has been suggested by many that in terms of regulating the use of drugs in sport there cannot be one system of doping regulation that applies equally to all sports because the nature of sporting activity varies; as the genetic code is unravelled, the issue for the sport will be the extent to which genetic manipulation is used to enhance prowess and performance (Grant,2006).

In recent years, the Algerian authorities have undertaken to fight firmly and by all means against doping practices in sport; Following the ratification in 2006 of the UNESCO International Convention against Doping in Sport and the creation of the National Anti-Doping Commission (CNAD) in 2011, the Algerian government adopted a new law 13-05 of July 23, 2013 relating to the practice of sport and including anti-doping

measures are a fundamental aspect of this legislation. : a person who cheats must be punished. Nevertheless, he or she must also be informed, prevented and protected from the health risks that doping can trigger; for this purpose, the CNAD plans, coordinates and implements anti-doping control in Algeria

and participates in the prevention and education activities implemented in the fight against doping (Kesri et al ,2018).

I.1. Literature Review

The cooperation between the international organizations to support and develop sport was one of the most successful models, but it is the best of all. Perhaps the field of cooperation of the International Olympic Committee (IOC), UNESCO and the International Anti-Doping Agency(WADA) to eliminate the phenomenon was one of the most wonderful and best examples in the history of international cooperation between organizations. The International Olympic Committee (IOC) can be seen as the usual carrier in the rapid construction and development of the World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA) in 1999 and now it stands as a hybrid public-private sector, funded and represented by both national and sports institutional bodies.. WADA's ability to control doping by setting standards, developing testing technologies, and administering controls for doping in sports on a global level stands as a model of transnational governance, WADA is a recognized, successful model of governance; the scaffolding of the anti-doping regime led by WADA has derived much of its authority by networking with other transnational governance actors, primarily the United Nations. Rather than acquiesce to the WADA Code, the UNESCO convention to combat doping in sport was signed, accepted, approved, or acceded to when governments met at the UNESCO General Conference in 2005, 191 countries. nation-states unanimously approved and ratified the International Convention against Doping in Sports. To be sure, this ability to elicit a unanimous approval from so many nations is remarkable. In this way, WADA centres itself as an expert regulator and "global standard-setter such as UNESCO, WADA got off the ground as a specialized global authority with the help of the IOC. As a transnational actor in its own right, the IOC threw its weight via incentives offered or withheld by making candidacy qualification to host the Olympic Games contingent upon a state's signatory status to the International Convention Against Doping in Sports (Casini,2009).

The theoretical background of the research expressed a cognitive framework for the regulatory and legislative aspects of institutions related to anti-doping programs.

We will detail the actors of UNESCO.

MINEPS International Conference of Ministers and Senior Officials Responsible for Physical Education and Sport

Created in 1976, MINEPS is the only global platform of its kind, engaging governments, intergovernmental organizations, the sport movement, academia and specialized NGOs. The outcomes and recommendations of MINEPS are continuously strengthening the educational, cultural and social dimensions of physical education and sport while guiding the implementation of effective policies and practices around the world (UNESCO,1976).

International Convention against Doping in Sport

These developments culminated in the decision by the UNESCO General Conference in 2003 to develop an international convention to remove doping from the sport. (UNESCO, 2004). the final Convention, adopted on 19 October 2005.

Complying with the Convention the objectives of providing an internationally recognised legal framework to:

- 1- ensure that governments take actions against doping in the sport
- 2-provide support for the Code and for other international standards developed by WADA,
- 3- Foster international cooperation between States Parties and with WADA in particular.

As of 31 December 2009, 131 governments have become States Parties to the Convention.

Articles (19-23). The Convention requires governments to support, devise or implement anti-doping education and training programs doping control procedures and relevant aspects of Code. Education on the potential risks posed by the use of nutritional supplements is specifically listed. For the sporting community, (Paul Marriott-Lloyd, 2010).

Fund for the Elimination of Doping in Sport

The Fund for the Elimination of Doping in Sport, established by Article 17 of the Convention, has been designed to ensure that all governments can play an active role in stamping out doping in sport. Dedicated funding has been set aside to help States Parties implement the Convention.

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Article 17 – Voluntary Fund -1. a Fund for the elimination of doping in sport, hereinafter referred to as the Voluntary Fund, is hereby established; the voluntary Fund shall consist of funds-in- a trust established by the financial regulations of UNESCO; all contributions by States Parties and other actors shall be voluntary. (UNESCO, 2005).

Since 2008, UNESCO’s Fund for the elimination of doping in Sport has invested more than \$4.2 million in projects led by 108 States Parties to the International Convention against Doping in Sport. This figure shows the output of the fund.

Figure 1: The distribution of Projects
Source: Conference of Parties (UNESCO 2017)

Since its inception, 21 States Parties have made contributions to the Fund. This means that the number of countries benefiting from the Fund is five times higher than the number of donors, representing a significant amplification concerning investment. Several of these countries have made multiple contributions (Australia, China, Finland, France, Kuwait, Luxembourg, Monaco, New Zealand, Russian Federation, Saudi Arabia and Spain).

Table 1: Return on Investment in the Fund for the Elimination of Doping

Year	Number of donors	income of
2007	11 donors	\$1,090,984.76
2008-2009	12donors	\$1,305,067.77
2010-2011	08 donors	\$1,542,281.56
2012-2013	07 donors	\$1,212,276.80
2014-2015	06 donors	\$638,922.73
2016-2017	06 donors	\$390,206.46

Source: Conference of Parties (UNESCO, 2017)

The Conference of Parties requested that priority be given to projects which enhance the capacity of least developed or low-income States Parties: applications from least developed States Parties or low-income countries, as

defined by the United Nations Economic and Social Council's Committee for Development Policy, are strongly encouraged, particularly given that this was one of the principal objectives behind the establishment of the Fund. (UNESCO, 2016)

Table 2: Fragile donor base

Region	States Parties	Donation (USD)	Donation (%)
Arab States	2	269,970	4%
Asia-Pacific	7	873,995	14%
Europe/North America	13	4,973,939	81%
Total	22	6,117,904	100%

Source: Conference of Parties (Meenakshi Set Al 2018)

We look at Figure 1 and Table 2, we note that Europe and North America, which is one of the richest countries, ranks third in terms of benefiting from projects and is classified as the least-contributing country in supporting the fund.

The Conference of Parties

The Conference of Parties has overall responsibility for the implementation of the Convention.

The relationship with WADA can be reviewed at the Conference alongside the mechanisms for funding its annual core budget; In addition to States Parties and the other Member States of UNESCO. (UNESCO, 2017).

The history of Algeria's accession to UNESCO

Algeria joined UNESCO the day after independence, October 15, 1962 (UNESCO, 2014).

Algeria was the 37th country in the world and the n^o 2 in Arab countries to ratify the International Convention against Doping in Sport and Algeria is considered one of the least contributing countries to support the fund, it contributed 1 051 330 USD during the UNESCO per biennium 2016-2017 (UNESCO 2017). and Algeria is one of the priority parties to the fund because it is considered one of the least developed country Parties (UNESCO, 2016).

II. Method and Materials

2.1. Participants

Details of the Algerian project

Committee Members warmly received the first Algerian project under the Fund and commended the linkage of planned activities with recent findings regarding an urgent need to increase knowledge and understanding of doping control procedures and nutritional supplements. Members positively

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The project. (UNESCO, 2015).

The opinion of the approval committee in the project submitted by Algeria Having examined the project submitted by Algeria (Request No.1314), approves funding of US\$ 17,571 for this project.

The objectives are to provide anti-doping education to athletes and support personnel ; to raise public awareness on doping consequences and prohibited substances; to establish local anti-doping committees and information centres.

Activities is an implementation of 4 one-day workshops in different cities, engaging athletes, coaches and sports officials; in parallel, development of information centres manned by education officers, medical staff and retired athletes; as a follow-up to the seminars, establishment of local anti-doping committees (based on volunteering). Local media and press releases to ensure project visibility (UNESCO, 2020).

Table 3: project of Algeria (Request No.1314)

Date of approval	October 2015
Type of project	National
Priority	Education projects focusing on youth and sports organizations
State party	Algeria
Title	Anti-doping information and awareness-raising workshops
Funding	US\$ 17,571
Beneficiaries	Athletes (600), coaches (120), sports officials (80)

Source: Projects-UNESCO's Fund for the Elimination of Doping in Sport (Maps).2020

2.2. Materials

The website of the World Anti-Doping Agency(<https://quiz.wada-ama.org/>) - computers - printers - questionnaire papers.

2.3. Design and Procedure

In this study, we test the general and specific knowledge of participants in the UNESCO Anti-Doping Program, registered under the number (1314); the sample is made up of 400 people, identified at random. It consists of four groups, each group includes 100 people. It is made up of a group of athletes, managers and coaches present at the level of four Wilaya (Province) located within the framework of the implementation of the program.

We are based on a questionnaire made up of 39 selected questions from the interactive program of the World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA, 2018).

A quiz is a game that consists of a questionnaire to test general or specific knowledge or skills. WADA's Play True Quiz is an interactive computer

game that tests athletes' knowledge about anti-doping. An integral element of its Outreach Program, WADA devoted considerable resources to the development of the interactive computer game which has been showcased at major events including the Olympics, Paralympics and many world championships. The Quiz is currently available in 43 languages. Start testing your knowledge (WADA, 2020).

The questionnaire adopted in our research included four main axes :

Axis related to athlete rights (09 questions)

Axis related to the duties of the athlete (09 Questions)

Axis related to athlete sanctions (11 questions)

Axis related to the prevention of athletes (10 questions)

We adopt a method of cognitive stimulation of the target elements in the study to achieve a response that includes feedback, to verify the stability of the information obtained from participation in the UNESCO program.

Feedback is information about the difference between the current level and the reference level of a system parameter; this information is used to change the deviation in some way.

We make it clear that we intentionally turned away from the aspect of sports ethics because it constituted a contradictory point in the athletic training program" Is it in the name of ethics that a coach teaches a footballer to "steal a penalty" or to "make cinema" by evoking an imaginary pain to gain (or lose) time ? No : it is in the financial or moral interest of the team and the club (Noret,1981).

More surprisingly, advanced medical expertise can take on the a priori irreconcilable roles of "doper" and controller. So we don't think so well when we say that modern sports medicine has played a major role in the refinement of the use of performance aids (Waddington, 2000).

2.4. Statistical Analysis

After emptying the results of the questionnaire, we obtained nearly 14% of the positive responses, which means that they were classified on the column (sufficient Theoretical background) and almost 86% of the responses were negative, which means that they are classified on the column (insufficient Theoretical background).

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The percentage of negative responses was distributed among the lines of inquiry as follows Rights (26%) - Duties (12%) - Sanctions (09%) - Prevention (39%).

Table 4: The questionnaire results

Axes	sufficient Theoretical background 14% (Positive)	insufficient Theoretical background 86% (Negative)
Rights	01%	(26%
Duties	03%	12%
Sanctions	08%	09%
Prevention	02%	39%

III. Results :

We have noticed that there is a variation according to the geographic variable in terms of positive responses due to the environment centred on sports practice and participation in high-level sporting events; we noted a weak awareness of the level of rights and prevention in the field of doping, which explains the lack of personal incentive (internal issuer) to protect against health risks and moral scandals related to doping.

Most professional athletes learn to accept or minimize pain while viewing injuries as part of the game. It is the threat of doping that comes to mind spontaneously. Taking performance aid products is inseparable from this activity (Laure,1995).

And confirmed this to us in a previous study, which we came to know perceptions about doping and the results are showing the majority of athletes have not had a correct help on the definitions of doping [doping to improve performance use of stimulant pharmaceuticals)] the majority of sportsmen did not have a correct help on the dangers of doping for health (there is no danger for health). the majority of athletes have never read the World Anti-Doping Code (I have never read or seen the content World Anti-Doping code exist just to punish me). the conditions which made it possible to constitute this concept at the Algerian sportsmen there are several social, cultural, political and economic factors) Kesri et al,2015).

We have noticed a relatively positive knowledge of the level of rights and sanctions, which explains the existence of an external incentive, because of the fear of punishment, the loss of professional career and the achievement of results. It should be noted that the athlete can be a victim of violence in the athletic field and at the same time is dominated by fear of doping control

measures (Atkinson M and Young K, 2008).

And as stipulated in the Code of Practice for Industry and periodic, which states the following: the press should avoid prior or offensive references to race, colour, religion, gender, sexual orientation, or any physical or mental illness or disability. • Details of race, colour, religion, gender, sexual orientation, physical or mental illness or disability should be avoided unless they are genuinely related to the story (Nigel and Andy,2009); however, there is nothing to prevent the media from spreading doping scandals and exposing athletes involved in doping issues to public opinion.

IV. Conclusion

The field of anti-doping in Algeria suffers from the absence of specialized and professional institutions.

Note that Algeria is classified in the group of Arab countries according to the UNESCO classification, and we can say that the Arab countries are the weakest in terms of contribution or benefit of the Anti-Doping Fund and unfortunately that Algeria only benefits one faith within the framework of the financial projects by the UNESCO fund during the year (2015)

Despite the existence of legislative texts supporting the financing of anti-doping projects in sport as confirmed by article 162 of law 13-05 (JO, 2013), the implementation mechanisms are blocked due to the lack of administrative and financial independence and also the lack of effective institutions such as the laboratory accredited by the World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA), all these difficult circumstances are strong indications of the difficulty of the missions for the fight against doping.

Finally, it can be said that the UNESCO project through the Anti-Doping Fund is very useful and important for governments, institutions, sport and athletes, but it requires continuity and follow-up to keep what has been achieved after the implementation of the project and the athlete should not be left alone in the field because Those looking for quick and unlawful gain will not leave the field empty and nature cannot tolerate emptiness.

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